

Healthy Ageing Diet Study

Volunteer for research at Queen's University Belfast and the University of Reading

Researchers are seeking to:

- understand how ageing affects food habits and nutrition awareness

You may be suitable to be interviewed for this study if you are:

- ✓ Living in the community in Northern Ireland or Reading, England (not in residential care)
- ✓ Aged 65+
- ✓ Able to complete a 60 to 90 minute interview in English
- ✓ Able to provide written consent

WHY GET INVOLVED?

- ✓ Share your lived experience of ageing and food
- ✓ You will help us learn what to prioritise in the development of foods to support healthy ageing

WHAT IS INVOLVED?

Participation will involve one 90 minute interview with a researcher in your home or convenient location.

CONTACT BARBARA BRAY BY EMAIL
OR PHONE

BBRAY01@QUB.AC.UK

07720 700297

Can you help with a research project

The Healthy Ageing And Diet study is currently recruiting older people in Northern Ireland and Reading, England

Researchers are seeking to:

- understand how ageing affects food habits and nutrition awareness
- explore food-based solutions to improve diets of older people

STUDY DETAILS

- A 90 minute interview in English at home or a convenient location with a researcher (Barbara Bray)
- Participants must be 65 and over and living at home (not in care)

HOW YOU CAN HELP

- Identify potential participants
- Share the participant information sheets and advertisement with eligible people

Contact Barbara Bray to get involved

Bbray01@qub.ac.uk

07720 700297

Interview Guide

NOTES TO INTERVIEWER:

- Do not read aloud anything in bold print.
- Use this guide to create a conversation that will allow the person to share his or her views, not as a question-and-answer oral survey.
- If the participant spontaneously answers a later question, allow that but also go back and ask about questions that appear earlier on the interview guide.
- Remember to summarise what you have heard at the end of each topic and wait for any additional thoughts or changes to what the interviewee has said.

INTRODUCTION

Hello. My name is Barbara Bray. I am the Researcher for the Healthy Ageing Diet study. The purpose of the interview is to learn more about your eating habits, food shopping and to see what types of foods you would be interested to buy in the future.

The interview will be recorded, and the words written into a document for research purposes, but these documents will be anonymous and not contain your name. The recordings will be destroyed when the typed documents have been prepared.

You may inform me if there are any particular statements that you do not wish to have transcribed at the end of the session.

There are no right or wrong answers; just your opinion based on your experiences. Any questions before we begin? **[Answer any questions.]**

Section 1

I'll start with questions about your experience of getting older and if this has changed your eating habits and the foods you enjoy.

- Can you tell me what foods you enjoy eating most?
- What are the main changes that have impacted your choice as you have been getting older?
 - (prompt -sensory decline, reduced appetite, dental problems, illness, more time to eat better)
- Have you noticed any changes to your appetite?
 - (prompt - In what way?)
- How do you think your eating habits have changed since reaching X years old?

Section 2

Now I would like to learn more about whether or not getting older has affected your food shopping and food choices.

- Tell me how you like to shop for food?
 - (prompt any help at home with food shopping?)
 - supermarket or online; how often?
- Do you ever have food delivered to your home?
 - (prompt - from supermarkets; fast food outlets; meals on wheels; special meal delivery services?)
- When do you make the decision about what to eat each day?
- How do you find what you are looking for in the shop?
- What factors influence your decision when selecting foods to buy?
 - (prompt - taste, cost, portion size, health, sustainability)
- Can you tell me if getting older has also influenced the food you select?
 - In what ways?

- Who prepares your food?
 - How does the cooking equipment and environment influence what you cook?
 - What difficulties or barriers do you experience in preparing food?
 - What improvements have you implemented in preparing food?
 - Who do you eat with?
 - Does what you eat vary depending on who you eat with?

Section 3

I'll now move on to discuss nutrition for healthy ageing and what you think is important.

- What does a healthy diet mean to you?
- What do you think are the most important foods, food groups or nutrients for healthy ageing?
 - (Prompt – vitamins, minerals etc)
- In your opinion, what are the barriers for you personally, to having a healthier diet?
 - (Prompt – cost of food, shelf-life, pack sizes)
- What foods do you find most convenient to eat?

Section 4

Now, lastly, I would like to know your opinions on the types of foods you would be interested to buy in the future.

- In an ideal world, what foods would you buy more of if you didn't have any barriers?
 - Prompt with barriers raised earlier in the discussion.
- What advice would you give to manufacturers if they were to design foods especially for older consumers?
 - Prompt – packaging/storage/ease of prep/reduced pack size

- Do you have any ideas that would help older people to shop for the foods they want and need?

Thank you. We're almost at the end of the interview.

Think back to everything we've discussed today. Is there anything you'd like to add to what's been said? **[Pause and wait for any new information.]**

Is there any topic or question you think that I left out of today's conversation that we should include? **[Pause and wait for any ideas.]**

Are there any comments in today's conversation that you would like to remove from the transcript? **[Pause and wait for any ideas.]**

What would you say is your key message or most important idea from today's conversation?
[WAIT FOR ANSWER] Why?

*****Document ends here*****

**QUEEN'S
UNIVERSITY
BELFAST**

Date: 23 January 2024

To: Dr Claire McEvoy

Faculty REC MHLS 24_26

Reference Number:

Full Title: Exploring UK older adult's perceptions of ageing related changes and their influence on food purchasing and food choice.

Thank you for your application for ethical review, which was received on 23 January 2024.

I can confirm that the application is valid and will be reviewed in accordance with the Proportionate Review process of the Faculty of Medicine, Health and Life Sciences Research Ethics Committee (MHLS Faculty REC).

Documentation Received	Version	Date
Ethics Application Form	1	23 January 2024
Research Protocol	1	15 January 2024
1. Participant Consent Form (SSI)	1	15 January 2024
2. Relative Consent Form (SSI)	1	15 January 2024
3. PIS (SSI)	1	15 January 2024
4. Demographic Survey	1	15 January 2024
5. SSI Topic Guide	1	15 January 2024
6. Distress Protocol	1	15 January 2024
7. Healthy Ageing Resource	1	15 January 2024
8. Recruitment Poster	1	15 January 2024
9. Partners' Recruitment Poster	1	15 January 2024
10. Community Visit Appt Check Form	1	15 January 2024
11. Lone Worker in Community Visit Log	1	15 January 2024
12. Lone Worker Risk Assessment	1	11 January 2024
13. Risk Assessment Driving	1	11 January 2024
Peer Review (HO'H)		19 January 2024
Peer Review (LMcG)		19 January 2024

If you would like to discuss this further, please contact me on facultyrecmhls@qub.ac.uk

Yours sincerely

Lorraine Carew

Research Ethics Officer
facultyrecmhls@qub.ac.uk

Participant Information Sheet Semi-Structured Interviews

Exploring UK older adults' perceptions of ageing related changes and their influence on food purchasing and food choice

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

1. **Introduction** The above-named research project is being conducted as a collaboration between the University of Reading, and Queen's University Belfast (QUB) in Northern Ireland, UK.
2. **What is the purpose of this study?** The study will explore the perceptions of age-related changes and factors affecting food behaviours in older adults aged 65 years and over.
3. **Why am I being invited to join the study?** You are being invited to take part in a one-time interview with the study researcher because you have the experience of being an older person i.e. aged 65 year and over, and you live independently in either Northern Ireland or England. Before you decide whether to join the study, you must fully understand why the research is being carried out and what your role would be. Please thoroughly read the following information. Discuss it with others if you wish. If you have any questions, contact the study researcher (contact information at the end of this form). Take your time to decide whether you wish to take part.
4. **Do I have to participate in this study?** No, you do not. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary; you do not have to take part in this study if you do not want to. If you decide to join us, you may leave the study at any

time without giving a reason. You will not experience any consequences from this in terms of your legal rights or participating in any future activities organised by the study team. After reading this information sheet if you decide to join us, you must sign a consent form before taking part in the research. We will ask for your continuing consent before you take part in any study activity, which you can give orally. All data will be anonymised (i.e., each study participant is given a unique identification code) that will be used during data analysis.

5. **May I ask a someone to complete the interview with me?** A family member/friend or carer involved in food purchasing or preparation can be invited to take part in the interview if they provide their written consent.

6. **What happens next if I want to take part?** A member of the research team will contact you by phone to answer any questions you may have. If you are eligible, they will schedule a one-time individual interview that is expected to last no longer than 90 minutes. This will take place in a convenient location which may be a dedicated research centre at Queen's University Belfast or University of Reading, your home, a local community centre or place of worship. The interview audio will be recorded on a laptop and backup portable device and the recording transcribed to a written document for analysis. The recording and the written document will be held in secure storage at Queen's University Belfast. When all analysis has been completed and checked by the research team, the recordings will be permanently deleted the software. You will be asked to sign the Informed Consent Form before taking part in the interview. Alternatively, the interview can be held remotely online if that is your preference.

7. **What happens if I agree and then I change my mind?** If you initially agree to participate you are still free to change your mind and not take part in the interview. There will not be any negative consequence. If you withdraw your consent after taking part in the interview and before the results have been

analysed, we will erase your recorded interview and not use any of your data in the analysis or research reports.

8. **What are the possible risks or disadvantages of taking part?** This study does not pose any great risk to anyone participating. In some cases, a person might be uncomfortable answering a particular question. If that happens, you can choose not to answer the question without giving any explanation or experiencing any consequence. If a question causes any distress, the interview will be paused, and will only proceed if and when you are ready.

9. **What are the possible benefits of taking part?** The study may be applicable to you or a member of your family. You will have an opportunity to share your lived experience and talk about your eating habits and food choices as you have grown older. Your participation will help researchers and policymakers better understand and improve the way that older people living in the UK can access healthy food. There is no payment for participating in this study.

10. **How will my taking part in the study be kept confidential?** No one will know you are in this study unless you tell them. At the start of the study, you will be given a unique ID code that we will use instead of your name. We will use that code on all study documents so no one will know what you have said. We will safely store all information including audio recordings and the transcripts we collect during this study and when all analysis has been completed and checked by the research team, the recordings will be permanently deleted from Microsoft Teams. Only the study team will see or use the information we collect. We will never use your name in any report we produce, further protecting your identity. We will store all information

securely for up to 10 years, following strict data protection rules at Queen's University Belfast. The information collected during the study will be stored in a locked cabinet in a locked office at Queen's University Belfast and any electronic information will be stored as a password protected file on a password protected computer from Queen's University Belfast. The information will be de-identified when it is shared with the project team so that no comment or information is directly attributed to you. After that time, the stored data will be destroyed following national guidelines.

11. Who is organising and funding the study? The study is part of a PhD programme under the FoodBioSystems theme on healthy ageing diets and is organised by Queen's University Belfast. It is funded by one of the UK's research council's, Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC).

12. Who has reviewed the study? The project has been reviewed by the Faculty of Medicine, Health and Life Sciences Research Ethics Committee, Queen's University Belfast (Ref: xxxxx).

13. What if there is a problem?

If you have any concerns about any aspects of the study, you should ask to speak to the researcher. They will do their best to answer your questions. If a suitable explanation is not provided by a researcher, then you should contact the chief investigator, Dr Claire McEvoy, Centre for Public Health, Institute of Clinical Science Block A, Queen's University Belfast, Grosvenor Road, Belfast, BT12 6BJ (see contact details overleaf).

Should you remain unhappy and wish to make a formal complaint, you can contact the Research Governance Team at Queen's University Belfast (Telephone: 02890 972529; Email: researchgovernance@qub.ac.uk).

14. What will happen to the results of the research? We will share what we learn with interested groups as reports or published articles in scientific

journals. If you want to receive a copy of the report, you can contact the researcher.

15. Summary The research team wish to thank you for taking time to read this Information Sheet. If you decide to participate, you will be given a copy of the Information Sheet and Consent Form for your own records.

16. Contact for further information. If you have questions or want to talk about the study, contact -

Researcher: Barbara Bray, PhD researcher Centre for Public Health, Institute of Clinical Science B, Grosvenor Road, Belfast, BT12 6BJ.

E-mail: bbray01@qub.ac.uk

Tel: 07720700297

Chief Investigator: Dr Claire McEvoy, Senior Lecturer, Centre for Public Health, Institute of Clinical Science B, Grosvenor Road, Belfast, BT12 6BJ.

E-mail: c.mcevoy@qub.ac.uk

This research will be conducted in compliance with data protection legislation. For more information about how we look after your information, how to access your rights and who to contact if you have any queries or concerns about data protection, please visit the Queen's University Belfast website

[List of Research Privacy Notices | Privacy Notice for Research Participants | Privacy Notices | Queen's University Belfast \(qub.ac.uk\)](#)

The researchers would like to thank you if you decide to take part in this study.

All volunteers will be provided with their own copy of this Participant Information Sheet along with a copy of the consent form which you sign.

RELATIVE CONSENT FORM Semi-Structured Interviews

Exploring UK older adults' perceptions of ageing related changes and their influence on food purchasing and food choice

Name: _____

Relationship to participant: _____

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the Participant Information Sheet Version 2 dated 16.02.24 for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I can confirm that I have been consulted about [*participant's name*] participation in the study. I understand why the research is being done.
2. I agree to accompany [*participant's name*] in the above study, inclusive of all the procedures mentioned in the Participant Information Sheet.
3. I understand that my participation is at the request of [*participants name*] and that we are free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, and without our legal rights being affected.
4. I understand that all information collected about [*participant's name*] during the course of the research may be looked at by responsible individuals in the study team at Queen's University Belfast, and the University of Reading. All data will be kept strictly confidential as necessary under the Data Protection Act and will be stored securely on University premises.
5. I agree that anonymised* quotations from recorded interviews with the researcher can be used in research publications.
6. I understand that myself or [*participant's name*] will not be identifiable in any data published in relation to this project.

Consent regarding future research studies (optional):

7. I agree to be contacted by the University about future research studies about diet or lifestyle and health.

Name of Relative	Date	Signature
Name of Participant	Date	Signature
Name of Researcher	Date	Signature

* Anonymised data is information that has been stripped of any personal identifiers, such as names or addresses, that could be used to identify an individual.

TITLE OF PROJECT: Exploring UK older adults' perceptions of ageing related changes and their influence on food purchasing and food choices.

Demographic survey

Please confirm your age, gender, ethnicity and where you live. The responses will help to explain people's eating behaviour and their food choices.

1. How old are you?

(Please select one)

- 65-74 years old
- 75+ years old

2. What best describes your gender?

(Please select one)

- Male
- Female
- Prefer to self-describe _____
- I'd prefer not to answer this question.

3. Where do you currently live?

(Please select one)

- Northern Ireland
- England
- I live outside of the UK.

4. Would you describe the place where you live as...

(Please select one answer)

- A big city
- The suburbs or outskirts of a big city
- A small city or town
- A country village
- farm or home in the country

5. What is your ethnicity?

(Please select one)

- White
- Chinese
- Irish Traveller
- Indian
- Pakistani
- Bangladeshi
- Black Caribbean
- Black African
- Black Other
- Mixed Ethnic Group
- Other Ethnic
- I'd prefer not to answer this question.

The next few questions are about your employment, education and relationship status.

6. What is your current employment status?

(Please select one answer)

- Full-time employee
- Part-time employee
- Self-employed / Freelance
- Unemployed
- Retired
- Other (Please specify)
- I'd prefer not to answer this question.

7. What is your highest level of education?

(Please select one answer)

- Primary Education or below
- Secondary Education (GCSE/GCE levels/ Intermediate / Junior/ Group Certificate or equivalent)
- Tertiary Education (Diploma/ A levels/ Leaving Certification or equivalent)
- Degree Level Education (Degree level or equivalent e.g. NVQ Level 4, Higher National Diploma or Certificate)
- Above Degree Level Education (Postgraduate degree/diploma or

higher (PhD)

- I'd prefer not to answer this question.

8. What is your current relationship status?

(Please select one answer)

- Single
- Married/Civil partnership/cohabiting.
- Separated/Divorced/Widowed
- In a relationship but not living together
- I'd prefer not to answer this question.

The following questions are related to your health status and appetite

9. How often do you have a drink containing alcohol?

Never	Monthly or less	2 to 4 times per months	2 to 3 times per week	4 or more times per week	
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10. How many units of alcohol do you drink on a typical day when you are drinking?

0 to 2	3 to 4	5 to 6	7 to 8	10 or more
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Alcohol unit reference

One unit of alcohol

Drinks more than a single unit

11. Are you following a special diet?

If yes, what type of diet are you on (tick all that apply)

Diabetic Diet	Weight reduction diet	Weight gain diet	Low fat diet	Cholesterol diet	Other medical diet	Other diet
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12. Was this diet recommended or prescribed to you by a doctor, nurse or dietitian or another medical practitioner? YES/NO

13. Do you describe yourself as vegetarian or vegan?

- Vegetarian
- Vegan
- Neither

14. My appetite is...

- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very good

15. When I eat, I feel full after...

- Eating only a few mouthfuls
- Eating about a third of a plate/meal
- Eating over half of a plate/meal
- Eating most of the food
- Hardly ever

16. I feel hungry...

- Never
- Occasionally
- Some of the time
- Most of the time
- All of the time

17. Compared when I was 40, I think that I can taste food...

- A lot better now
- A bit better now
- The same as when I was 40
- A bit less now
- A lot less now

18. Compared when I was 40, I think that I can smell odours (for example, when walking in the forest, smell of cooking, etc.) ...

- A lot better now
- A bit better now
- The same as when I was 40
- A bit less now

- A lot less now

19. Do you suffer from any illness?

YES/NO

If yes, please give details:

20. Do you take any form of dietary supplement e.g., fish oils, vitamins or minerals?

YES/NO

If yes, please give details:

Supplement name	Dose	Frequency of use
Evening Primrose and other plant oils		
Folic acid		
Iron (with and without vitamin C)		
Calcium (with and without Vitamin D)		
Multivitamins		
Vitamin C		
Vitamin D		
Cod liver and other fish oils		
Non-nutrient supplements including herbal		
Other nutrient supplements		

21. Do you smoke?

YES/NO

If yes, please give details:

DISTRESS PROTOCOL

INVESTIGATORS:

Ms B Bray¹, Dr ME Clegg², Prof JA Lovegrove², Prof JV Woodside¹, Dr CT McEvoy¹

1. Centre for Public Health, Queen's University Belfast
2. Partner 1, University of Reading

TITLE OF PROJECT: Exploring UK older adults' perceptions of ageing related changes and their influence on food purchasing and food choice.

Participant Distress protocol

This protocol will be applied if a study participant indicates distress with any of the topics under discussion.

1. Identify participant distress

A participant indicates they are experiencing a high level of stress or emotional distress OR they exhibit behaviours suggestive that the discussion/interview is too stressful such as uncontrolled crying, shaking etc.

2. Researcher response

Stop the interview.

Offer immediate support and assess mental status: e.g. Tell me what you are feeling right now? Do you feel you are able to go on about your day?

3. Review

If participant feels able to carry on; resume interview.

If not, discontinue interview.

Encourage the participant to contact their GP or healthcare provider OR

Offer, with participant consent, for a member of the research team to do so.

Offer to call a relative or care provider to assist with transport home.

4. Follow-up

If participant consents, follow up with courtesy call the following day OR

Encourage the participant to call either if he/she experiences increased distress in the hours/days following the interview.

Modified from: Draucker C B, Martsolf D S and Poole C (2009) Developing Distress Protocols for research on Sensitive Topics. Archives of Psychiatric Nursing 23 (5) pp 343-350